

Intussusception Secondary to Colonic Lipoma in Terminal Ileum in A 48-Year-Old Woman: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Intussusception of the small intestine in adults is rare, representing 5% of all intussusceptions and causing 1% to 5% of intestinal obstructions in this population. Colonic lipomas are benign mesenchymal neoplasms and represent the second most common non-epithelial tumor of the colon after adenomas. Since most cases of intussusception in adults present with a benign or malignant pathological point of origin, surgical intervention remains the standard of care.

Case report: We report the case of a 48-year-old female patient with no prior medical history who presented with intestinal obstruction secondary to intussusception caused by a colonic lipoma located in the terminal ileum. She underwent surgical treatment, had a successful postoperative course, and her progress over the following three months was satisfactory.

Discussion: Intestinal intussusception is defined as the invagination of a proximal segment of the intestine into a distal segment. Primary adenocarcinomas are the most frequent cause of colonic intussusception, while lipomas are the predominant benign lesion. The authors recommend surgical intervention as the primary approach for complicated lipomas, especially sessile lipomas, where endoscopic excision would be technically difficult.

Conclusion: Intussusception is an uncommon condition in adults. The causes of intussusception can be benign or malignant, with colonic lipoma being an infrequent entity. The importance of this case report lies in demonstrating the surgical management and its evolution, since, being an infrequent condition, there are no formal guidelines or standards regarding the surgical approach to follow.

KEYWORDS: Intestinal invagination, colonic lipoma, intestinal intussusception, sessile lipoma, intestinal obstruction.

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INTRODUCTION

Intussusception of the small intestine in adults is rare, accounting for 5% of all intussusceptions and causing 1% to 5% of intestinal obstructions in this population. This condition is more common in children and, in adults, is usually secondary to a pathological shunt. In the small intestine, the causes are diverse and can be due to intraluminal or extraluminal masses such as polyps, lipomas, or other intestinal lesions. (1)

Intestinal lipoma, a rare disease first described by Bauer in

1757, is a benign, non-epithelial, slow-growing fatty tumor. (2) Colonic lipomas are benign mesenchymal neoplasms and represent the second most common non-epithelial tumor of the colon after adenomas. Histologically, they are composed of mature adipose tissue located within the intestinal wall, most frequently in the submucosa. Its reported prevalence in clinical and autopsy studies ranges from 0.2% to 4.4%, reflecting its relatively infrequent, but not exceptional, occurrence. (3)

Adult patients with intussusception often present with signs of bowel obstruction, and abdominal contrast-enhanced computed

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tomography (CT) is the test of choice for diagnosis and surgical planning. Since most cases of intussusception in adults have a benign or malignant pathological shunt, surgical intervention remains the standard of care. (4)

Colonic lipomas do not show significant sex predilection and can arise throughout the gastrointestinal tract, although they predominantly affect the colon. Within the colon, the most frequently affected sites include the right colon and cecum (39.6%), followed by the transverse colon (25%). (5) A colonic biopsy is usually necessary to confirm the diagnosis of intussusception caused by a colonic lipoma. This avoids the misdiagnosis of inflammatory changes surrounding the lipoma as inflammatory bowel disease. (6)

Both surgical and endoscopic resections have good results, with no known recurrence after complete excision.

Surgery is the only available method for large lesions or those affecting the muscular or serosal layers. Colotomy or segmental resection of the colon is indicated when the diagnosis is definitive. Conversely, segmental resection, hemicolectomy, or subtotal colectomy is recommended when the diagnosis is doubtful or a complication occurs. In fact, only histopathological analysis of the tumor can provide a definitive diagnosis. (7)

Given its low incidence, diagnostic difficulty, and limited reported surgical experience, it remains important to document and analyze new cases of this rare entity. The objective of this report is to describe the case of a 48-year-old patient with an intussusception, managed with right hemicolectomy with ileocolic anastomosis resection, highlighting the clinical, diagnostic and intraoperative findings, as well as the favorable postoperative result.

CASE REPORT

We present the case of a 48-year-old mestizo woman from Campeche, Mexico, a housewife with no history of chronic degenerative or surgical illnesses. She denies alcohol consumption, smoking, or illicit drug use. She has a standard diet with normal carbohydrate and fat intake. She is not physically active. She lives with her husband and three children, with adequate family and psychosocial support. There is no family history of intestinal disorders, genetic diseases, or other relevant illnesses. She reports previous hospitalizations for pyelonephritis, managed with inpatient medical treatment.

The patient began experiencing symptoms 36 hours before surgery, with generalized abdominal pain, associated with nausea and vomiting of gastrointestinal contents, abdominal distension, and passage of intestinal gas. She was treated with butylscopolamine for the first 12 hours of her illness, but the pain worsened, localizing to the pelvic region, with increased nausea and vomiting, and she was unable to have a bowel movement. She therefore sought hospital medical attention.

The physical examination reveals a patient with mild dehydration, normal thoracic and cardiac examination, a

distended abdomen, tender to palpation in the pelvic area, and no stool present on rectal examination. A urinary catheter is in place with clear urine present, without urinary sediment. A nasogastric tube contains approximately 100 cc of apparent fecal matter, with no improvement in abdominal distension or pain. There are no signs of hypovolemic shock.

Laboratory studies showed leukocytosis of 19.40 ($10^3/\text{mm}^3$), neutrophils 92%, hemoglobin 14.3 g/dL, platelets 396 ($10^3/\text{mm}^3$), blood type O+, aPTT 26.7, PT 11.4, INR 1.04, C-reactive protein 1.04 mg/dL, Na 137 (mmol/L), Cl 106.4 (mmol/L), K 3.95 (mmol/L), Mg 2.0 (mmol/L). Arterial blood gas analysis showed pH 7.34, pCO₂ 42 mmHg, PaO₂ 13 mmHg, and lactate 4.0 mmol/L. Due to the insidious onset of abdominal symptoms, with a significant elevation of leukocytes and abnormal blood tests, a computed tomography scan of the abdomen and pelvis was performed for a probable diagnosis of acute appendicitis versus intestinal obstruction.

A computed tomography scan was performed, revealing the following radiological findings (Figures 1, 2, and 3).

Figure 1. Axial reconstruction of an abdominopelvic computed tomography scan showing several slices sequentially. The area of intussusception is shown with a red arrow.

The CT scan report confirms intussusception, so an exploratory

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laparotomy is performed.

Figure 2. Coronal reconstruction of an abdominopelvic computed tomography scan showing several slices sequentially. The intussusception area is shown with a red arrow. The large intestine is delineated in red, and the wall of the intussuscepted area (small intestine) is delineated with yellow arrows.

The preoperative prognosis was favorable due to the absence of comorbidities, as well as the absence of previous surgical interventions.

Figure 3. Comparison between axial and coronal section. The area of intestinal invagination is shown in the red circle.

The exploratory laparotomy was performed under balanced general anesthesia, with the patient in the supine position. A midline supra- and infraumbilical incision was made. Tissue dissection was performed until the abdominal cavity was reached, where clear free fluid was found, with no evidence of intestinal perforation or free intra-abdominal fecal matter. A systematic exploration of the cavity was performed from the ligament of Treitz to the ileocecal valve. In the small intestine (terminal ileum), 30 cm proximal to the ileocecal valve, a mass of approximately 5 x 5 cm was found (Figure 4). The mass was soft in consistency and pedunculated into the intestinal lumen. It is important to note that, at the time of surgery, the ileocolic intussusception was reduced using small bowel retraction. The small and large intestines showed no significant color changes. There were no changes in ischemia or necrosis at the time of surgery.

Figure 4. The lipoma area is shown, with the pedicle extending towards the antimesenteric wall of the small intestine. The histopathological report confirms that it is a pedunculated colonic lipoma.

Due to the lack of a definitive diagnosis and the possibility of malignancy, a right hemicolectomy and distal ileum resection were performed. Forty centimeters of distal ileum and ascending colon were resected (simple right hemicolectomy), and a side-to-side mechanical anastomosis was performed using 75mm intestinal staples, anastomosing the ileum to the transverse colon. The abdominal cavity was irrigated, the absence of intestinal leakage was confirmed, and the surgical procedure was completed.

Surgery duration: 101 minutes. Surgical blood loss: 150 milliliters. Intraoperative urine output: 25 ml. Total fluid intake: 900 ml and output: 1080 ml. The patient was extubated without complications and subsequently transferred to the general surgery ward.

During the first 24 postoperative hours, the patient maintained a

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blood pressure of 114/63 mmHg, SpO₂ of 98%, and a heart rate of 68 beats per minute. Antibiotic treatment was administered with Ceftriaxone 1 gram intravenously every 12 hours and Metronidazole 500 mg intravenously every 8 hours. Postoperative analgesia was managed with Paracetamol 1 gram intravenously every 8 hours and Ketorolac 30 mg intravenously every 8 hours.

The postoperative course was satisfactory, with antibiotic and analgesic management throughout the 7 days following surgery. The patient was kept NPO (Nothing by mouth) and received intravenous fluids for four days. On the fifth postoperative day, a liquid diet was initiated, followed by a soft and normal diet.

Gas drainage began on the second postoperative day.

Stool was first passed on the third postoperative day.

The patient was discharged from the hospital on the seventh postoperative day, tolerating oral intake, with adequate gas drainage, and with bowel movements.

During follow-up at one, two, and three months, the patient remained free of recurrence of pain, functional limitations, or obstruction, with a full return to her daily activities. In the six weeks following the operation, medical evaluation confirmed the absence of recurrence, good integration into a normal diet, and aesthetically satisfactory healing without local complications or hernias. From the patient's perspective, the outcome was satisfactory. No infections, seromas, hematomas, anesthetic complications, or late adverse events were observed. Furthermore, she was reassured by the pathology results, which confirmed an intestinal lipoma with no evidence of malignancy or swollen lymph nodes.

The histopathological report confirms a pedunculated colonic lipoma with no evidence of malignancy.

DISCUSSION

Intestinal intussusception is defined as the invagination of a proximal segment of the intestine (intussusceptum) into a distal segment (intussusciens), adopting a telescopic configuration. This phenomenon can cause intestinal obstruction, interrupt blood flow to the affected segment of the intestine, and lead to complications such as intestinal necrosis, perforation, or sepsis. The etiology of intussusception in adults is identifiable in 70% to 90% of cases, with primary adenocarcinomas being the most frequent cause of colonic intussusception, while lipomas are the predominant benign lesion (8).

Colonic lipomas are rare, with an incidence ranging from 0.2% to 4.4% among benign colonic tumors. They are most frequently found in the right colon, particularly the cecum and ascending colon. Although more common in older adults, they can occur at any age. Most lipomas are submucosal and asymptomatic, although subserosal and intramural variants exist. Lesions larger than 4 cm, termed "giant lipomas," are more likely to be symptomatic. (9)

In a single lipoma whose size and weight increase over time, distortion of the colonic wall or luminal obstruction can create

a pressure gradient and disrupt normal peristaltic activity, pushing the affected segment of the colon toward the adjacent segment, causing intussusception. Regarding treatment, the authors recommend surgical intervention as the primary approach for complicated lipomas, especially sessile lipomas, where endoscopic excision would be technically difficult. (10) Initial diagnosis is challenging, particularly in distinguishing a colonic lipoma from a malignant neoplasm. Abdominal ultrasound can be used initially for diagnosis, although it is operator-dependent and requires an experienced radiologist, especially if the lipoma measures less than 2 cm. Computed tomography is useful for the diagnosis of colonic lipoma. (11)

CONCLUSION

Intussusception is an uncommon condition in adults, causing intestinal obstruction in these patients and accounting for 5% of all bowel obstructions. The causes of intussusception can be benign or malignant, with colonic lipoma being a rare entity (between 0.2% and 4.4% of all colonic tumors). In this case, we report a 48-year-old female patient with no prior medical history who presented with intestinal obstruction secondary to intussusception caused by a colonic lipoma located in the terminal ileum. The importance of this case report lies in illustrating the surgical management and its outcome, since, being an uncommon condition, there are no formal guidelines or protocols regarding the appropriate surgical approach. In this case, early diagnosis (<24 hours) with computed axial tomography, surgical management (resection of distal ileum and right hemicolectomy with side-to-side ileotransverse anastomosis) was successful and with a satisfactory evolution at 3 months.

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Conflict of interest: None declared.

Ethical considerations: The patient received complete information about the diagnosis, procedures, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures, as well as for the publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the hospital's institutional regulations.

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